

**ILMIY VA
INNOVATSION
TERAPIYA**

**SCIENTIFIC >>> >>>
AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

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VASCULAR ENDOTHELIUM. WHAT IS THIS? WHAT IS ITS ROLE AND WHAT IS ENDOTHELIUM DYSFUNCTION?

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Abstract. The endothelium is a single layer of cells lining the inner surface of blood vessels. Endothelial cells perform many vascular functions, including vasoconstriction and dilation, to control blood pressure.

All cardiovascular risk factors (hypercholesterolemia, arterial hypertension, impaired glucose tolerance, smoking, age, excess weight, sedentary lifestyle, chronic inflammation and others) lead to dysfunction of endothelial cells.

Keywords: эндотелий, ангиогенез, дисфункция эндотелия, гипоксия, ГЛИКОЛИЗ.

The vascular endothelium plays an important role in the regulation of vascular tone under normal conditions and in various diseases. The term “endothelial function” usually means the regulation of capillary blood flow, carried out due to the dynamic change in phases of vasoconstriction and vasodilation of resistive type vessels in accordance with the needs of cellular metabolism [1, 2], respectively, “endothelial dysfunction” is a violation of the regulation of the dynamic response of blood vessels in response to appropriate stimuli. Endothelial dysfunction underlies many pathological conditions, such as atherosclerosis, arterial hypertension, preeclampsia [1–3].

Endothelial cells (EC) are cells of the inner lining of blood vessels and play an important role in the process of tissue respiration and metabolism. Normal adult ECs remain largely quiescent but can be rapidly activated in response to injury or pathological conditions where angiogenesis is required [4]. Angiogenesis is regulated by three main subtypes of ECs that perform specialized tasks: angiogenesis-initiating cells, which direct vascular process growth in response to growth factors; stem cells that grow and lengthen the shoot; resting cells that are present in newly formed vessels and regulate vascular homeostasis and endothelial barrier function [5, 6]. The review presents literature data on EC function and dysfunction. We searched and analyzed published full-text review and original articles in foreign (English) and Russian languages using the eLIBRARY.RU, Google Scholar, Web of Science, Scopus and PubMed databases for the period from 2004 to 2021. Priority was given to original articles, dedicated to studies of the state of the endothelium, as well as its changes in various diseases in humans. The following keywords were used for the search: endothelium, endothelial dysfunction, endothelial physiology.

Process of neovasculogenesis. The vascular network is formed earlier than all other organs during the process of ontogenesis and subsequently matures into a closed complex system of vessels of various diameters. All organs and tissues of

the body, with the exception of cartilage tissue and the cornea, depend on the blood flow necessary for vital processes [4, 7].

The process of vasculogenesis begins early in embryonic development. Mesodermal angioblasts unite to form primitive vascular-like tubes lacking a wall; hemangioblasts also take part in the process of primary angiogenesis, subsequently differentiating into endothelial and hematopoietic cells [8, 9].

Subsequent remodeling of the vascular bed is achieved by two mechanisms: intussusception and vascular sprouting. Intussusception leads to expansion of the capillary bed due to the “division” of the capillary into two adjacent vessels, while the opposite walls of the primary vessel protrude into its lumen, ECs come into contact with each other to form a local endothelial bilayer, with existing connections between ECs. Pericytes and myofibroblasts cover the resulting hollow transcapillary column, which increases in circumference, dividing the capillary into two parallel vessels [10].

Vascular sprouting occurs as a result of increasing tissue demand for oxygen, which stimulates the production of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), fibroblast growth factors and other proangiogenic factors. VEGF stimulates receptors on the surface of the endothelium, resulting in local relaxation of the vessel, destruction of contacts between endothelial cells, separation of pericytes and destruction of the basement membrane. Next, migration of endothelial cells occurs and elongation of the future vascular sprout occurs. At the same time, terminal and stem ECs are differentiated [11].

Despite the fact that the germination process occurs from the EC of the same vessel, the terminal and stem cells in the developing vessel differ both functionally and morphologically. Terminal cells have numerous filopodia and projections consistent with their highly mobile behavior, whereas stem cells have relatively few filopodia [12].

Interestingly, the EC, which is the germination initiator cell, “imposes” the phenotype on the cells through the expression of the Notch ligand Delta-like 4 (Dll4). In neighboring ECs, Dll4 binds Notch receptors, causing the release of the intracellular Notch domain and driving the expression of the VEGF receptor (VEGFR1), while reducing VEGFR2 expression. An increased VEGFR1/VEGFR2 ratio reduces the sensitivity of ECs to VEGF and “imposes” a stem cell phenotype [14].

Features of endothelial cell metabolism. In the metabolism of EC, the main role is played by the process of glycolysis, which has a number of advantages over oxidative phosphorylation: firstly, the high rate of glycolysis supports the production of lactate, which functions as a proangiogenic signaling molecule. Secondly, reactive oxygen species are maintained at minimal levels, while the amount of oxygen available for transfer to tissues remains at sufficient levels [17]; thirdly, dependence on glycolysis creates the prerequisites for EC germination in an avascular, hypoxic environment, where interstitial glucose levels do not limit the rate of the process [18].

The activity of the glycolysis process is directly dependent on the stimulation of VEGF, which are able to increase the level of expression of glucose

transporter 1 and glycolytic enzymes, such as lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) A and bifunctional 6-phosphofructo-2-kinase/fructose-2,6-bisphosphatase-3 (6-phosphofructo-2-kinase/fructose-2,6-bisphosphatase 3, PFKFB3). The latter is a regulator of glycolysis and uses its kinase activity (which is 700 times greater than phosphatase activity) to produce fructose-2,6-bisphosphate, which allosterically activates the rate-limiting glycolytic enzyme phosphofructokinase-1. Although genetically determined deficiency or chemical inhibition of PFKFB3 only partially (40%) reduces glycolysis, this is sufficient to significantly impair EC germination in vitro, as well as vascular branching and proliferation in vivo. In mature endothelium, there is a decrease in glycolysis activity and a decrease in the number of mitochondria, which determines the functional rest of the endothelium [19].

It should be noted that the number of mitochondria in the endothelium is approximately 2–6%, while in hepatocytes they contain 28%. However, during the transition from the resting state to angiogenesis, oxygen consumption in the EC increases 3 times. In this case, the work of endothelial mitochondria is consistent with the Crabtree effect, in which lower glucose levels (~1 mmol/l) cause increased mitochondrial respiration with opposite effects (growth inhibition and decreased respiration) at high glucose levels [25].

Features of lipid metabolism in endothelial cells. Endothelial cells are not only capable of accumulating lipids, but also independently synthesizing them. Since triglyceride synthesis enzymes are located in the endoplasmic reticulum, de novo formation of lipid droplets presumably occurs in its membrane. If necessary, lipids are hydrolyzed to form fatty acids with the participation of adipose tissue triglyceride lipase, hormone-sensitive lipase and monoglyceride lipase [13]. Caveolins (Cav-1–3) are coat proteins that govern the biogenesis of caveolae, i.e., microdomains of lipid rafts with a flask-shaped protrusion structure of 60–100 nm. Loss of endothelial Cav-1 impairs lipid droplet formation through increased lipolysis by hormone-sensitive lipase, which may explain why Cav-1-deficient mice are protected from atherosclerosis. The formation of lipid droplets in EC is necessary to prevent lipotoxicity, ensure the process of β -oxidation of fatty acids to reduce the intensity of the glycolysis process and release fatty acids from EC into neighboring perivascular cells [26].

Thus, ECs take an active part in lipid metabolism: lipid synthesis in ECs is necessary for their migration; inhibition of acetyl-CoA carboxylase shifts the lipid composition of EC membranes towards increasing the level of polyunsaturated fatty acids, which reduces membrane fluidity, filopodia formation and EC migration. The presence of lipids in EC can cause endothelial dysfunction: oxidized phospholipids increase the secretion of purines, while in order to maintain cellular ATP levels, EC increase glycine synthesis through the regulation of mitochondrial methylenetetrahydrofolate dehydrogenase/cyclohydrolase. ECs transport lipids to other cells. The fatty acid translocase FAT/CD36, which is responsible for the transfer of fatty acids across the cell membrane, is important in this process. Within the EC, lipids are either free as fatty acids or bound to fatty acid binding proteins, which transport fatty acids to their destinations [27].

Thus, the vascular endothelium plays a vital and ubiquitous role in vascular homeostasis by regulating the transport of cells, nutrients, and metabolites between the bloodstream and underlying tissues. Diabetes mellitus, obesity, dyslipidemia, smoking can cause endothelial dysfunction, the manifestation of which can be: damage and loss of integrity with increased permeability of the vascular wall, induction of the synthesis of cytokines and adhesion molecules, metabolic disorders, creation of a prothrombotic environment, cell dedifferentiation [20].

Functioning of the endothelium under hypoxic conditions. During tissue hypoxia, the expression of hypoxia-inducible factors (HIF factors) increases due to prolyl hydroxylase domain (PHD). PHD requires oxygen to hydroxylate the HIF α subunit. During hypoxia, PHDs lose the ability to hydroxylate HIFs due to their enzymatic dependence on oxygen, and the loss of this degradation mechanism results in the activation of a HIF-mediated transcriptional program that includes the induction of angiogenesis, glucose metabolism, and is considered an important factor in the development of malignancies. HIF transcriptionally functions as a heterodimer consisting of HIF α and HIF β subunits that binds to the hypoxia response element in the promoter of target genes. In most cell types, HIF-1 is expressed during acute hypoxia. The transition from HIF-1 to HIF-2 is observed in the case of chronic hypoxia, despite the fact that most genes are regulated by both factors simultaneously [32]. HIF-2 α increases the expression of tyrosine phosphatase, which in turn reduces V-cadherin phosphorylation, maintaining bond integrity, and prevents loss of endothelial barrier function [15]. The expression of HIF-1 α in alveolar ECs enhances the inflammatory response and promotes cell-mediated inflammation with activation of CD4 $^{+}$ and CD8 $^{+}$, and also increases the expression of the proinflammatory cytokines interleukin (IL) 2 and tumor necrosis factor- α , which suppress CD55, resulting in increased complement-associated endothelial damage. In addition, HIF-1 α of myeloid cells is a key factor in cell activation under conditions of hypoxia and inflammation by modulating cellular energetics, activating glycolytic enzymes and glucose transporters, which allows the generation of ATP under hypoxic conditions and prevents apoptosis of innate immune cells. However, in chronic infections, HIF-1 α prevents excessive lymphocyte recruitment into the lung interstitium and immunopathological consequences for the host. Increased number of circulating EC progenitors positively correlates with patient survival [22].

Conclusion. The presented review of literature data allows us to once again outline the problem of endothelial dysfunction, to see that the endothelium is a unique structure that regulates the activity of the entire macroorganism, and dysfunction of the EC is an important pathogenetic mechanism underlying the genesis of various diseases. Despite the fact that there is information about markers of endothelial dysfunction, such as HIF, VEGF, in our opinion, further search for new markers applicable in routine clinical practice is necessary. Of course, an important direction is the search for therapeutic correction strategies.

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